

Attach no., square, area and level to label on bag.

No.	Square	Area	Co-ordinates		Level	Remarks	Feature Data sheet no.	Present location	
			'E'	'N'					
1	(RZ)	NE			① (RZ ⑥)	White Packed Gypsum Fill w. Charcoal Flecks	Fd1		
2		NE			①	Burnt Gypsum	Fd2		
3		NE			①	Sand Gypsum with Limestone Frags.	Fd3		
4		NE			①	Limestone Frags, 1 Pottery Frag, 1 Dolomite Chip	Fd3		
5		NE			①	TAN CLAY-LIKE sand	Fd7		
6		NE			②	Gypsum	Fd7		
7		NE				Gypsum - hard in chunks	Fc3		
8		NE				Burnt (Red) Gypsum - Charcoal	Fc17		
9		NE				Copper Filings	Fc17		
10		NE				Gypsum Fill	Fc17	Univ. of Louisville	K. Lal Gauri
11		NE				Copper Filing	Fc19 sub cutting		
12		NE			②	Gypsum w/ Limestone Frags	Fc22		

Season GS 79

Site SPHINX
SANCTUARY

*Soil/Floatation/Organic material/Inorganic material/Palaeomagnetic/C¹⁴ sample register, page: _____
*Delete where necessary. Use fresh sheet and numbering for each type of sample.

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			'E'	'N'					
13		NE			②a	Yellow Gypsum	Fc22		
14		NE			①	Compact Brown Clay	Fc22		
15		NE			① LOOSE SAND	Limestone Frags, 1 Sherd ND	Fh1		
16		NE				Small Limestone Frags 2-3 small Sherd Frags	Fh4		
17		NE			②	Small Granite, Limestone chips	Fh5		
18		NE			③	Large Limestone chip, smaller limestone chips, Granite chips, Dolomite chips, Flint	Fh5		
19		NE			③	Granite, Limestone "gravel" after sifting	Fh5		
20		NE				DRIED INSECT REMAINS	Fh5		
21		NE				GYP SUM	Fh13		
22		NE				Limestone Frags, 1 small Granite chip	Fh13		
23		NE			① SURFACE	1. Red ware sherd	Fh14		
24		NE			①	TAN CLAY	Fh14		

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			'E'	'N'					
25		NE			①	CARBON	Fh14		
26		NE			②	Grey Fine Packed clay-like soil	Fh14		
27		NE			②	Large limestone chip	Fh14		
28		NE			②	Fragment Thick Walled Red Ware Pot	Fh14		
29		NE			②	CARBON AND SHERD FRAGMENTS	Fh14		
30		NE			②	Granite, Dolerite, Limestone, Sherd Fragments	Fh14		
31		NE			② ②a	Small Bone Splinter	Fh14		
32		NE			② ②a	Small Sherd Fragments	Fh14		
33		NE			②a	SOIL - Ash? Fine Grey	Fh14		
34		NE			②a	1 Sherd ND	Fh14		
35		NE			①	PACKED TAN CLAY	Fh15		
36		NE			①a	Gypsum	Fh15		

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			'E'	'N'					
37		NE			①-②	CARBON	FH15		
38		NE			②	FLINTS (Flakes)	FH15		
39		NE			②	Light Grey Clay - Gypsum mix (?) Fine - Soil	FH15		
40		NE			②	Light Grey Clay - Gypsum mix (?) Fine Soil	FH15	U.S.	
41		NE			②	Chert - Flint Fragments	FH15		
42		NE			②	Small granite, pottery frags.	FH15		
43		NE			②a	Small shard frags, limestone frags 1 possibly diorite (?)	FH15		
44		NE			②b	CARBON	FH15		
45		NE			②b	Fine Light Grey Soil AFTER (Clay - Gypsum mix?) SIFTING	FH15		
46		NE			②b	Gravel - stone Material After Sifting Mostly Limestone, Some Granite	FH15		
47		NE			②b	3 small shards NO	FH15		
48		NE			2b	YELLOW CLAY	FH15		

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P:photographed/ D:drawn/T:typed

OBJECT NO.	SQUARE	AREA	CO-ORDINATES		LEVEL	DESCRIPTION AND REMARKS	P/D/T	PHOTO. NO.	PRESENT LOCATION	
			'E'	'N'					ANT. REGISTER	MUSEUM NO.
49.	Fh15	NE			(2b)	SEED, HUSKS, POD IMPRESSIONS			U.S.	
50.	Fh15	NE			(2b)	STONE FRAGS - GRANITE DOLERITE				
51.	Fh16	NE				Gypsum from Upper Edge of Hole				
52.	Fh16	NE			(1)	SAND-GYPSUM MATRIX				
53	Fh16	NE			(1)	Granite, Sherd, Limestone FragS.				
54	Fh16	NE			(1) (2)	Reconst. Fragment O.K. type CRW Vessel				
55.	Fh16	NE			(2)	Large Frags Stone Material Granite-Limestone-Dolerite				
56.	Fh16	NE			(2)	Grey clay-Gypsum Mix(?) "Granite Dust"				
57	Fh16	NE.			(2)	SOIL - AS ABOVE AFTER SIFTING				
58	Fh16	NE			(2)	"Gravel" - small stone Material After Sifting; Granite-Limestone				
59.	Fh16	NE			(2)	MUD SPOT				
60.	Fh16	NE			(2a)	Concentration Gypsum on Bottom				

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			'E'	'N'					ANT. REGISTER	MUSEUM NO.
61	Fh17	NE				"Yellow Gypsum" from top of Hole				
62	Fh17	NE				Gypsum below ① - Tan clay				
63	Fh17	NE				TAN CLAY				
64	Fh17	NE			①	TAN CLAY				
65	Fh17	NE			③	"GRANITE DUST"				
66	Fh17	NE			③	STONE MATERIAL				
					③a	Granite - Dolerite chips				
67	Fh17	NE			②	GYPSUM			U. of Louisville K. Lal Guori	
68	Fh17	NE			③	"Gravel" STONE MATERIAL				
					③a	Granite Limestone AFTER SIFTING				
69	Fh17	NE			③	Fine Grey soil AFTER				
					③a	Clay - Gypsum Mix (?) SIFTING				
70	Fh17	NE			③	Limestone, Granite, Dolerite				
					③a	Inclusions				
71	R12	NE				Compact Tan clay from under cbc W side (NS 78 R12)				
72	R3	NE				Packed concentrated stone chips in sand under cb1 - ST NW corner block (NS 78 R3)				

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			'E'	'N'					ANT. REGISTER	MUSEUM NO.	
73	R3	NE				Large Stone Material From Concentrated Stone Chips in Packed Gravely Sand under cb1 - S.T. NW corner Block, S side (NS 78 R3)					
74	R3	NE				"Gravel" STONE MATERIAL After sifting from above locus. # No. 72					
75	R3	NE				Same as above No. 74					
76	R5	NE			(4a)	IRON ORE FRAGMENT (NS 78, R5, N Bolk, (4a))					
77	R5	NE			(5)	CARBON Space Between cb1, cb2 S.T. NW corner (NS 78 R5, (5))			U.S.		
78	R5	NE			?	Space Between cb1, cb2, ST NW corner - First Cleaning - Contamination?	METAL FOIL				
79	R2	NE			(5)	IRON FRAGMENT					
80		N-NW				Efflorescences, Flakes from Core Body, N side			U. of Louisville	K. Lal Guari	
81		NW-SW				Flakes, efflorescences exposed bedrock core - Rump upper edge			"		
82		E				Flakes Fallen from Chest - Bedrock core			"		
83		E				Soft Clay-like or Ferruginous Vern exposed Bedrock Core N Forepaw, inner (S) side.			"		
84		SW				Efflorescences, Flakes, Causeway Embankment - W end			"		
SEASON					SITE		OBJECT REGISTER, PAGE: _____				

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			'E'	'N'					ANT. REGISTER	MUSEUM NO.	
85.		S.T.				Scrappings efflorescences w Niche Face - Pedrock, Sphinx Temple			U. of Louisville K. Lal Gauri		
86		NW				Patina - efflorescence on Face Pedrock Quarry Ledge - NW Corner Sanctuary					
87.	R5	NE			⑤	1 Sherd					
88.	R2	NE			⑤	5 Sherds 1 Diagnostic					
89.		N				SHERDS STONE FRAGS (NS 78) N Major Fault Dump Removal					
90.		NE				Fill Between cb 1, cb 2, S.T. NW Corner (TAN CLAY-LIKE SAND?) * →	2 Granite Frag - + smaller chips 1 Dolerite Frag 3-4 Sherds - including frag base CRW conical vessel				
91		NE				Red Ware Sherds w black painted Design - From inadvertent clearing of sand foundation of mud floor fronting SW corner Amenhotep II Temple during NS 78 Dump clearing					
SEASON						SITE		OBJECT REGISTER, PAGE: _____			

* On basis of soil still adhering